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The Disease Burden in Fish Farm Management: An Integrative View and a Specific Vision in Europe

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ABSTRACT

In aquaculture, the interactions and balance—or imbalance—between the fish, the rearing environment, pathogens, and farm management determine the occurrence and impact of clinical diseases. The global assessment of the factors related to disease impact is commonly referred to as disease burden. This assessment goes beyond the economic consequences of mortality and morbidity, encompassing additional economic factors related to disease management, as well as broader social and political consequences. The concept of disease burden is gaining relevance in aquaculture, where disease poses serious threats to animal welfare, productivity, and economic sustainability. At the farm level, the consideration of fish as living assets includes aspects such as direct mortality, indirect effects of mortality, and morbidity. Furthermore, the impact of disease on key performance indicators, routine operations, and planned productivity are important consequences. Diseases on fish farms also require effective management, whether through the implementation of treatments or through preventive and biosecurity measures, both of which can have indirect impacts that must be properly analyzed. In many cases, the risks associated with disease necessitate appropriate surveillance by farms or regulatory authorities, and the cost of such surveillance and insurances should be considered part of the overall disease burden. Other important aspects such as the impact on animal welfare, wellbeing of farm staff, integration of the concept into certification schemes, and issues related to social perception, acceptance, and prestige are also examined. In addition, macroeconomic factors such as market impacts, governance, and a special emphasis on the One Health approach are addressed.

1 | Introduction

A disease is a transitory or permanent alteration of the structure, function, or activity of all or part of an organism. For living organisms, including humans or terrestrial and aquatic farmed animals, diseases are an almost inevitable reality during their lifetime, whose negative effects could be considered as disease

impacts, consequences, or also widely described under the idea of disease burden [1, 2]. Disease is also intimately linked to the concept of risk [3], mainly related to the quantitative and qualitative aspects. The concept of disease risk is widely considered in specific areas such as in epidemiology and risk assessment. In many cases, zero risk does not exist; the same applies to diseases. Therefore, in many cases, the main target is to minimize

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risks and the associated consequences (the burden) as much as possible. However, the specific aspects of these impacts and consequences are not so frequently addressed and visualized. Disease prevention and disease impact remediation are the two main strategies adopted to fight and control human, animal, and plant diseases, and the adoption of these strategies should also be considered as a part of this total burden. However, the concept of burden is even wider. The term “disease burden” usually refers to the impact of single or general health problems as measured by financial cost, mortality, morbidity, or other indicators. However, disease burden can also be considered as the impact and consequences of general or specific health problems mainly at an economic level [4], but also at many other societal [5] and even environmental levels [6, 7]. Disease burden has been widely addressed and studied in the scope of human diseases and society, not only in terms of basic indicators such as mortality or morbidity but also the economic impact, which can be quantified using standard indicators and metrics such as quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) and years lost due to disability (YLDs) (summarized in Moreno-Ternero et al. [8]). In contrast with human health, the impact of many infectious diseases, the environment, and the effect of human activities play a major role in the impact of diseases in the context of animal health [9]. The influence of humans, particularly in animal farming, creates new conditions for different intraspecific and interspecific interactions that may trigger new disease scenarios [10]. Disease burden in terrestrial farmed and domestic animals has been widely addressed, mainly for the aspects related to the economy [11]. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations' (FAO) perspective on the impact of diseases in agriculture and animal farming is mainly addressed to diseases as a relevant threat to the access of food [12]. The World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) addresses the idea of the disease burden from a general point of view in the Global Burden of Animal Diseases concept (GBADs), including livestock [2, 13] and recently in aquaculture production systems [14]. Disease burden in the livestock sector has become increasingly important to aid decision-making on how to best allocate resources for disease management [15]. Animal health economics addresses three main aspects: quantifying the financial effects of animal diseases, implementing methods for optimizing decisions when animals, herds, or populations are affected, and determining the costs and benefits of disease control interventions [16]. Usually, the economic cost of a disease is divided into direct and indirect costs, where the first refers to losses due to the impact of the disease (e.g., deaths, reduced growth, poor zootechnical performances) and the second to expenditures related to control measures (e.g., treatment) and forgone revenue [17]. Moreover, the costs of a disease may be experienced by individual farmers, livestock sectors, and/or by society, and therefore, the level of analysis must be established. For example, an outbreak of a zoonotic disease could also have a direct impact on the health of consumers and an impact on the increase in the prices of food products. In contrast to terrestrial animals, disease burden in aquatic animals has been much less addressed and studied [18–22]. Some of the factors that can be involved in this limited focus on the disease burden of aquatic diseases are probably related to, compared with terrestrial farming, the relatively recent development of aquaculture as an animal farming activity. The development of aquaculture, and particularly fish, crustacean, and mollusk farming in the

last 50 years, has been very fast and, in some cases, frantic, and deserves calmer analysis.

The aim of this document is, therefore, to offer an extensive overview of the state of the art in the concept of disease burden and in the impact of the diseases affecting aquatic animal farming, with a particular focus on fish farming. Although many of the concepts expressed in this review can be applied globally, most of the situations and examples indicated correspond to the current scenario of the European fish farming industry and in some cases, the specific scenario of the fish farming industry in the European Union (EU) and associated countries.

2 | Global Aspects of Fish Diseases Burdens

The potential impacts and burden of fish diseases can be assessed from different points of view. When the impacts are focused only at a farm levels, these impacts mainly affect the activity, operational performance and economy of the farm or fish farming company [22, 23]. However, when a specific fish disease expands and affects many farms in a specific area, region, or country, the impact of this disease can be relevant and strategic for an industry, sector, or even at national or international level. In these cases, concern about the disease should be assumed by regional, national, or international authorities that should develop specific strategies and policies on diseases surveillance and containment [14]. These approaches are well known in the context of terrestrial animal diseases, where extensive regulatory framework and supporting institutions have been developed worldwide. Particular mention should be addressed to the work done by the FAO and the WOA in their role to harmonize the surveillance and at an international level, focusing on both terrestrial and aquatic animals. This includes the development of the WOA/OIE Aquatic Manual, Diagnostic Code, documents on guidance for the assessment of an aquatic animal disease for a listing decision, health strategy plans and different reports on specific diseases and activities of the different commissions. The assessment of the worldwide relevance of fish health by developing lists of relevant and notifiable diseases is one of the more relevant activities. The system used to prioritize diseases is through a standard operating procedure or SOP [24], based on the selection criteria in The Aquatic Animal Health Code. Different criteria are described, some of them with an epidemiologic basis, but also a group of three relevant criteria described as “consequence criteria” are strongly linked to the concept of “disease burden”. These three main criteria correspond to concepts such as “significant production losses,” “significant morbidity or mortality in wild species,” and “the agent is of public health concern.” The later not only includes zoonotic potential but also other aspects related to public health, including environmental issues. These criteria are also aligned with the GBADs concept [14], as well as the GBADs programs developed by the WOA. These general criteria are considered as the main reference guidance to assess the impact of aquatic animal diseases and in the implementation of policies for surveillance and control in different countries.

In some cases, the fish farming industry has become a strategic activity for certain economic sectors in a region or country. In many countries, aquaculture represents a high percentage of the gross domestic product (GDP) [25, 26]. In fish farming,

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) represents one of the most produced species (2,863,700 tons during 2022, according to GLOBEFISH) and the farmed marine fish species with the highest value, from US\$ 10.10 billion in 2013 (according to FAO in 2014) to more than US\$ 20 billion in 2022 (based on average NASDAQ prices and production), Norway and Chile being the two main producers. In Chile, salmon production represents 2.1% of the GDP, second to copper mining [27]. In Norway, salmon farming is one of the largest industry sectors after petroleum and gas and represents around 2.3% of the GDP [28] and around 75% of the country's total seafood export value [29]. Scotland is also a relevant salmon producer in Europe, with 205,393 tons produced in 2021 [30]. In all these countries, the salmon farming industry was particularly impacted by Infectious Salmonid Anemia (ISA) outbreaks in the past and is currently affected by other diseases such as sea lice infections and Salmonid Rickettsial Septicemia (SRS) [31–33]. The impact of the economic crisis on Chilean finfish farming associated with the ISA outbreaks between 2007 and 2010 was particularly severe and analyzed from an economic point of view [34]. In a similar way, the economic impact of ISA and other viral diseases in the UK was also described [35, 36]. Chronic diseases may also have a significant economic impact. Additionally, substantial economic issues are linked to parasitic infestations, such as the costs of managing and controlling sea lice (*Lepeophtheirus salmonis*) in Norway [37], as well as the expenses and challenges associated with antibiotic use to treat SRS [38]. In such cases, the financial burden related to disease management can become a serious problem for the industry. In these cases, the crisis associated with certain infectious diseases causing massive mortality outbreaks in extensive areas such as ISA outbreaks [39] can become a serious problem for the industry, inducing serious financial problems, social problems due to unemployment, potential environmental risks, and an increased risk of industry failure. This jeopardizes the future and prestige of the national fish farming industry and undermines consumer confidence.

Fish diseases can also strongly affect the fish farming sector in a wider and global sense. Severe mortalities, forced fish culling or restrictive measures in the live fish trade to avoid the spread of a relevant infectious fish disease can affect the availability of fry or stocks and consequently, affect fish market prices. There are some recent examples of this and maybe the most well-known are the impacts of ISA outbreaks in Scotland (1998–1999 and 2008–2009) and Chile (2007–2010) on global market stocks, with relevant impacts on the price of salmon and the consequent market positioning value of salmon as food product. For all these reasons, the level of awareness of the relevance of the impact and associated burden of diseases has increased and has been translated into better health assessment and management policies and regulations. From a European perspective, countries like Norway and Scotland have developed strong strategies [40, 41] to prevent the impact of diseases in farmed salmon and protect the economic viability of the salmon farming industry. In the EU, the awareness of the impact of diseases in aquaculture and the fish farming industry is also reflected in the Farm-to-Fork strategy [42], as well as reflected in the Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases (Animal Health Law). In several parts of this regulation, aquatic animals, diseases and procedures are particularly addressed.

3 | Impacts of Fish Diseases and Public Health: A One Health Approach

As commented in the introduction, the concept of the GBADs may include several aspects, including the direct impacts on the farming activity, the impact of the diseases on the availability and quality of animal protein sources, and the increase in higher costs of animal products at a global level, as well as the impacts on society and even on the environment [13]. In some cases (zoonotic diseases), animal pathogens can also be transmitted to humans, causing also direct impacts on the human population. For this reason, one of the WOAH criteria to assess the relevance of animal diseases in the Aquatic Animal Health Code is whether the causing agent is of public health concern [43]. In contrast with literature concerning zoonotic diseases in terrestrial vertebrates [44], only a small number of papers have been published concerning zoonotic aquatic animal diseases (see Antuofermo et al. [45] and references herein), although very few of these papers contribute verified data about the real impact in number of cases or the economic impact in human health. In addition, there is sometimes confusion between zoonotic diseases from aquatic animals and waterborne or foodborne diseases, that in many cases have completely different aspects. Related to fish, the most commonly reported example of a zoonotic aquatic animal disease is Anisakiasis or Anisakidosis (see Adroher-Auroux and Benítez-Rodríguez [46] and references herein). This is a disease typically associated with the ingestion of wild aquatic animals, mainly fish but also invertebrates such as crustaceans and cephalopods that can act as an intermediate/paratenic host. However, the potential risk of oral transmission from farmed fish is highly minimized as farmed fish are fed with feed pellets. Even in cages, transmission is still possible by small, infected prey animals that pass through nets; nevertheless, the probability that a farmed fish can become infected by this nematode is very low and almost zero in fish reared in more controlled systems [47, 48]. Concerning viruses, no zoonotic viruses have been described, so far, affecting fish and humans. The situation of bacteria is slightly different but similar in terms of impact as true zoonosis. Among the different reported cases of bacterial infections in humans, only a limited number of reported clinical cases in humans are related to those species affecting fish [49]. Moreover, in even fewer cases, the strains affecting fish and humans were the same. In many of these cases, these putative cases of infections in humans are related to the presence of bacteria in the aquatic environment, foodborne transmission, or related to contamination during fish and shellfish processing or storage. For this reason, and compared to terrestrial farmed animals, farmed fish pose a significantly lower risk in terms of potential zoonotic diseases and pathogens. In these cases, further impacts such as costs associated with medical assistance and the costs associated with the disability induced by the disease should be considered. As an example, total medical expenses for Anisakiasis in South Korea were limited to US\$ 57,000 in 2011 and rising to US\$ 206,000 in 2018 [50].

Another very important potential impact related to the One Health concept, is the environmental impact of diseases. These impacts can be summarized into the impacts due to the transfer of pathogens to aquatic wildlife and the effects on aquatic

ecosystems, and the potential impact of the release into the environment of several substances and compounds used in the fish treatments. The circulation of pathogens between wild and farmed fish populations is particularly important in the aquatic environment [51–53], especially in farming conditions with scarce biosecurity measures, such as in cages or ponds. Many times, farmed fish have been claimed to have been the main source for pathogens and their dispersal into the environment [54], and indeed, in some cases, the effects are detected in wild populations and commonly in commercial fisheries [55]. The multiplication of pathogens such as viruses, bacteria or parasites generally tends to be magnified in farmed conditions, mainly due to the presence of high biomasses of fish in the farming units. Such is the case of parasites with a direct cycle such as copepods or monogeneans. Higher parasite loads under farming conditions usually spill back, intensifying parasite levels in the surrounding waters, leading to serious consequences in wild fish without appropriate health management, increasing mortality and, in the most severe cases, resulting in declining populations. The best-known example is the sea louse *Lepeophtheirus salmonis* in Atlantic salmon, which represents a major problem in aquaculture, constituting a cost equivalent to 9% of salmon farm revenues [56] and whose impact on wild salmon populations has been demonstrated several times (Liu et al. [57] and references herein). Another example is the disease produced by the monogenean *Gyrodactylus salaris*, a WOAHL-listed disease and a well-known cause of catastrophic damage to wild Atlantic salmon stocks after its introduction in Norway for aquaculture purposes, which led to the need for a coordinated intervention to manage it. The impact of this parasite in Norwegian rivers represents more than 55 million dollars a year in surveillance, eradication, and other losses associated with fishing, related industries, and tourism [58]. However, apart from the economic impact, the relevance of the negative impacts on the natural ecosystems [52], which are usually hard to identify and quantify, should not be overlooked.

Other relevant issues related to the environmental impact of diseases are those related to the impact of treatments used to control fish disease. The inaccurate use of antibiotics, antiparasitic substances, and other substances to treat and control fish diseases in farms has been claimed to potentially affect the organisms present in the aquatic environment surrounding the farms [59–62] as well as a source for the generation of antibiotic resistances [63]. However, these substances can also originate from other pollution sources such as industrial waste, agriculture, terrestrial farming, or urban wastewater. In any case, to reduce or suppress the potentially negative impacts of fish disease treatments in aquatic environments, the development of specific policies and strict supervision strategies is necessary. The EU and other European countries are particularly sensitive to these impacts and, as for terrestrial farmed animals, the use of medicinal substances in treatments in European countries is regulated by the corresponding prescriptions and authorizations and is under strict surveillance by national and international authorities such as the European Medicine Agency (EMA). In this sense, European legislation requires all veterinary medicines to undergo an environmental risk assessment (ERA) of the possible hazards to the environment, based on the expected use of veterinary medicines.

4 | The Societal Impact of Fish Diseases

Diseases on farmed fish may also have a relevant impact on society, and in the media, and should be considered part of the disease burden. The awareness of society concerning aquaculture and fish farming activities is not always the same and may vary between countries, including those in Europe [64]. In some cases, fish farming is appreciated as a safe, sustainable, and efficient source of high-quality protein and other nutrients [65–68] but, in other cases, the perceptions are different and not positive [69, 70], mainly due to sustainability and welfare issues. Fish diseases and disease management are closely related to these negative aspects. The impact on sustainability has already been described in the section on the environmental impacts of treatments, and in recent years, welfare issues are gaining relevance in terms of public perception and opinion. Environmental issues related to fish farming are particularly present in social media as they are in the spotlight of environmentalist associations and NGOs but also, in some cases, of professional and sport fishermen when diseases are responsible for the decline of natural fish stocks. High mortality rates, physical injuries, and distress associated with the diseases, ineffective prevention and diagnosis of diseases and physical disturbance or injury, ineffective treatments and stress, injuries or pain associated with the treatment of diseases, are the most frequent claims related to fish welfare in fish farming [71]. All these aspects can reach relevant impact levels in society and can affect the reputation of fish farming. The fish farming industry is also becoming much more sensitive to and proactive towards these problems, considering them part of the economic burden. Reputation, whether at a farm, company, or industry level, is sometimes an intangible asset that cannot be easily associated with a clear economic value but, without doubt, is a relevant factor in disease burden that should be considered. Other relevant impacts at the societal level are those related to the economic impact for the sector, described in the previous sections.

5 | Disease Burden and Governance

Disease burden can be studied from a very specific framework, such as a fish batch or a farm, up to a much broader point of view, such as the whole fish farming sector or industry at the national level or even at supranational or international levels. These wider viewpoints also require a specific approach, with special attention given to aspects related to a broader economic and social impacts analysis that would allow the development of specific strategic recommendations for development and governance. In these aspects, the FAO plays a fundamental role as an international organization with a relevant focus on aquaculture and fish diseases. Examples of the socio-economic impacts of different diseases, such as those affecting finfish aquaculture in Asian countries [72], highlight the relevance of these impacts in national aquaculture industries. At a similar level, the WOAHL covers many aspects of fish diseases, health, and welfare and has a special focus on the visualization of all the aspects related to the burden of disease through the GBADs, as described in the introduction. All these general concepts developed and addressed by the FAO and the WOAHL are also mirrored in international and national institutions. In Europe, the European Commission and European Food

Safety Authority (EFSA) are also focusing on animal disease burden from different points of view and supporting studies in this area. As aquaculture and fish farming are considered a relevant driver in the Blue Economy concept and in the Farm to Fork strategies, the elements included in the disease burden concept will be key in the future for the development of European strategies on aquatic animal health. In the same way, the relevance of the disease burden for fish farming has also been addressed in other European countries like Norway [40] and Scotland [73]. A special view should also be addressed to the many drawbacks in the EU associated with the presence of officially notifiable diseases according to the European legislation (Article 5 of Regulation (EU) 2016/429, Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/925 and Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/216) in the facilities. In these cases, even if there is no clinical disease in the facilities, the detection of certain pathogens may lead to different levels of restrictions, mainly affecting the movements of the fish in the same farm or between farms or even, in the worst-case scenarios, requiring massive culling. The costs associated with culling operations can be very relevant and should also be benchmarked with the benefits at the farm and regional level [74]. The operational restrictions imposed by the legislative framework have similar effects as described before.

6 | Specific Aspects of Fish Disease Burdens

6.1 | Economic Aspects

In livestock farming assessment, the main economic impact is based on the concept of interference in productivity. For farmers, their gold standard is to achieve the maximal productivity potential of the production system through the characteristics of the animals (genetic and epigenetic traits, productivity potential, and health), feeds, and general rearing conditions. When diseases occur within the farming system, they may interfere with all the biological mechanisms related to this productivity and trigger negative effects in the performance of the farmed animals. Some mathematical models about damage and diseases in terrestrial animal farming have been developed [75] and recently, novel approaches based on the concept of the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) based on the GBADs have been developed [2]. These models are based on how diseases can affect different variables such as the cost of the animals, the cost of food, potential growth, food conversion ratios, managerial costs, the value of the produced animals or how diseases can introduce new variables in concepts like revenue and gross margins. Some economic modelling aspects in aquatic animal diseases and health have been recently described [22], whilst focusing on the specific issues of these impacts in two cases: a rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* farm on Lake Titicaca, Peru, and a shrimp farm in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam. Some other specific studies on the direct economic impact of diseases in European sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax* farming have been recently published [76]. These theoretical models can be valuable to understand the effects of a single disease or a set of diseases in the economic balance of a farm. However, these models should always be validated through the analysis of real farm data from several production batches and, if possible, enriched by data from other farms operating in similar conditions.

In this way, it is possible to generate economic algorithms that can adjust the exact mathematical relationships between all the inputs. To operate the different economic formulas or algorithms, most of the items are not well referred to as values, and the concept of value in the case of fish farmed animals is not easily defined and sometimes not well differentiated. Maybe the most direct and clear aspect of the concept 'value' could be the 'market' value, or in other words, the value when the asset (live aquatic animals) can be sold in a market. The most classical example of 'value' is the value of the harvested animal (live, whole, and gutted) as a price per weight unit, such as Euros or Dollars per Kg, pound, metric ton or other weight measures. This value is highly variable according to species but also according to harvest size, quality, seasonality, and fluctuations in the market. For many farmed aquatic animals, harvesting is the only moment of their life cycle with a certain market value. In some species and according to the characteristics of the farming system, there is also a specific market for specific sizes, such as eggs, fish juveniles, or salmon smolts for the grow-out phase. However, for the rest of the life/production cycle, a clear, single "market value" does not exist. In fish farming, global stock market prices and trends for some species are publicly available (e.g., salmon and Nasdaq, FAO's open platform Globefish, EU public platform EUMOFA) or can also be traced through private data platforms. The availability of public data about the most relevant farmed species from local platforms and markets for the distribution and commercialization of food products, seafood electronic marketplace platforms, regulated marketplaces, or other specialized platforms, is usually much more limited. Access to the data available from these platforms usually works on a subscription or payment basis. For all these reasons, sometimes it is particularly difficult to assign defined values to fish stocks during the farming process.

In many cases, the quantification of the burden of the disease requires a comparison with a standard, which is represented by the productivity indicators in the absence of the disease. These productivity indicators are represented by the so-called general performance indicators that should be well defined and validated mainly through comparative studies. Performance indicators are well described and defined for different terrestrial farming systems [77–80]. Some of these indicators are mainly related to productivity, nutrition, and reproductivity performance, and some of them are also used together to compare in situations with specific health disorders such as abortions, metritis, or lameness, among others. These indicators are used, together with general and specific welfare indicators, as measures of the quality of life of farmed animals.

In fish farming and aquaculture, several general [81, 82] indicators have also been described, and specific indicators are currently used and recorded in most fish farms as part of their routine performance follow-up. In Mediterranean aquaculture, most of these indicators have been recently defined, analyzed, and prioritized for standard European seabass and gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) farming [83, 84]. Most of these performance indicators are currently used in other farmed fish species. Amongst these KPIs, several subcategories of KPIs can also be described, such as technical, economic, environmental, and also health- and welfare-related KPIs [83], and those that can be useful for use as disease-related indicators are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1 | List of potential health-related indicators useful to assess disease pressure and impacts used in fish farming.

Indicator	Description/formula	Uses	Source
Specific growth rate (SGR)	$SGR = (\ln W_f - \ln W_i \times 100) / t$ lnWf = natural logarithm of the final weight lnWi = natural logarithm of the initial weight t = time (days) between lnWf and lnWi	Production indicator. Indirect potential disease indicator	Marino et al. (2018)
Feed conversion rate (FCR)	$FCR = \text{Feed given} / \text{animal weight gain or Feed delivered} / (\text{biomass1} - \text{biomass0})$	Production indicator. Indirect potential disease indicator	Marino et al. (2018)
Total (aggregated) mortality (Batch/whole farm) (Period, day, week, month)	Total cumulative mortality recorded in a batch during the rearing period	Health indicator. Related to a specific disease or a specific disease event	Marino et al. (2018)
Malformations and discarded fish	Total malformed fish/total number of fish in the batch	Welfare indicator. Mainly for hatchery and nursery periods.	Kourkouta et al. (2022)
Mortality per disease/outbreak	Total cumulative mortality recorded in a batch during the rearing period	Health indicator. Related to a specific disease or a specific disease event	Marino et al. (2018)
Mortality first 3 days/10 days	Total cumulative mortality recorded in a batch during the 3 days after a transportation or event with intense manipulation	Health and Welfare indicator. Related to unspecific mortality/survival related to transportation conditions.	Marino et al. (2018)
Survival estimation	Number of alive fish from a batch at the end of the rearing period/number of fish in a batch at the beginning of the rearing period	Health and Welfare indicator. Related to losses due mortality but also to unaccounted losses and escapees.	Marino et al. (2018)
Unaccounted losses	Total number of fish introduced in the rearing system—harvested fish—mortalities and accounted losses	General indicator. Related to fish lost and not recorded during the production period: lack of precision of counting systems, escapees, spoiled/degraded dead fish, theft.	Marino et al. 2018
Vaccinated fish by disease	Percentage of vaccinated fish by disease/total number of produced fish x100	Related to vaccination capacity.	Marino et al. (2018)
Number of treatments (antiparasitic/antibiotic) against one specific disease per production batch or per year	Number of antiparasitic or antibiotic treatments per batch or year	Assessment of dependency of treatments for certain diseases and indirect indicator of the pressure of a certain disease	Marino et al. (2018)
Total amount antiparasitics and/or antibiotics used in each production batch or per year or per produced MT	Number of antiparasitic and/or antibiotic treatments per year in a rearing period or a year or per MT	Assessment of dependency of treatments and indirect indicator of the disease pressure in the facility	Marino et al. (2018)

For certain fish diseases, there are other well-established disease-specific indicators such as lesion score indexes, as in amoebic gill disease (AGD) in Atlantic salmon [85], macroscopic parasite counts, as in sea lice, *L. salmonis* [86] or *Sparicotyle chrysophrii* counts in gills, as in gilthead seabream [87] that can be used. Other data such as discarded fish during post-harvesting sorting

processes can also be considered as potential disease indicators at farm level.

Not all these performance indicators, and specifically health and welfare-related indicators are unanimously adopted by all veterinarians, aquatic animal experts, fish farms or companies

TABLE 2 | Main economic impacts of fish mortalities and the description of their characteristics.

Burden associated with mortality	Description
Total loss of the value of the fish	Value of the fish (market value/potential value)
Partial loss of the value of the fish	If the carcass of the fish can be used as animal byproduct (usually much lower value)
Costs of mortality removal, transportation and disposal	Personnel, transportation, storage and waste management costs
Reduced production capacity of the batch	Production batch with reduced number of fish. Productivity potential of the facility underused

for all scenarios, and are rarely used at the same time. Only some of the indicators are useful for specific fish farmed species, farming systems (extensive, RAS) or production phases (hatchery, grow-out), so different indicators can be used in different situations. Most farms and companies systematically collect and record these data in their own databases mainly for internal use and evaluation, allowing internal comparison of the production performance between batches or in temporal series. However, data on health indicators do not always allow direct inter-comparative studies between different farms, as they do not all operate with similar standards.

Nevertheless, the availability of public data on the values of these health indicators at farm level, unless they are included in public surveys, is still a major constraint. Today, it is still difficult to obtain information, even about the current values or normal ranges on farms. This is mainly due to the reluctance of companies to share publicly this data, as for example in the case of mortalities, unless the confidentiality about the origin of the data is completely guaranteed. This unwillingness to share this kind of data is understandable as this data are very sensitive for the competitiveness and the prestige of the farms and companies, but the lack of availability of public open data related to these indicators is still a serious handicap for the global assessment of the health performance of the fish farming sector.

In Europe, there are remarkable initiatives focusing on displaying public data from governments (Annual Fish Health reports from the Norwegian Veterinary Institute) and also from companies on mortalities issued by Salmon Scotland (<https://www.gov.scot/publications/fish-health-inspectorate-mortality-information/>) or by BarentsWatch (<https://www.barentswatch.no/fiskehelse/>), based in salmon farming. Concerning international and national authorities, in addition to databases provided by the World Animal Health Information System—WAHIS portal developed by the WOAHA, in Europe there are other databases and information that originate from international, national or regional surveillance programs, or occasionally from research projects. However, these open databases from surveillance cases focused only on notifiable diseases and unfortunately do not cover non-notifiable diseases, which usually represent the main bulk of losses due to diseases at farm level and in normal farming conditions.

6.2 | Mortality/Survival

Amongst all the health-related performance indicators, mortality and survival are the most widely used health and welfare

indicators in fish farming [88]. Mortality can be defined regarding a specific disease, outbreak (mortality associated with a disease event), as mortality regarding a specific period, farming stage or activities (mortality during larval rearing or mortality during smoltification in salmonids or after transportation), or as total aggregated mortality in a batch production unit or farm. Because the number of fish reared in fish farms and production units is usually very large (thousands and sometimes, millions of individuals), precision in the assessment of mortalities is not as easy as in terrestrial livestock farming. In some cases, mortalities can only be estimated, as for example in larval units, nurseries or in ponds. In hatcheries and nurseries, hundreds of thousands or millions of larvae, postlarvae or juveniles are reared in each tank and even the daily mortality can only be estimated due to the small size and fragility of the fish. In large ponds, mortalities are also difficult to detect and collect because of the size of the pond and low water transparency, unless morts (dead fish) are found floating on the water surface. In these situations, biases in the assessment of mortality are not uncommon. Another relevant factor to consider is the lower survival rate (sometimes so-called as ‘natural’ mortality) in some production periods, mainly in hatchery and nursery. In these periods, part of the stock (weak, non-adapted specimens) cannot survive, so in these periods, survival rates tend to be lower than in other farming periods like grow-out. In addition, in many fish farms, unaccounted losses due to cannibalism, predation, escapees, or lack of precision in the fish counting systems are also frequent problems, as these unaccounted losses can be mistakenly considered as mortality in the survival assessment. For all these reasons, the evaluation of losses during these periods should be appropriately considered to avoid incorrect interpretations regarding mortality and survival [89].

Mortality, from a basic point of view, represents a handicap for the farm as it has a direct impact on the objectives of the fish farm, but it should be highlighted that the burden related to mortalities goes beyond that of simply the loss of a living asset. The different types of burden associated with mortality are summarized in Table 2.

The main objective of a fish farm is to produce a valuable final product (at harvest) using production techniques that allow a good cost–benefit balance according to the targets of the company. Any mortalities represent not only a reduction in the total harvesting capacity and a loss of the resources invested in the dead fish, but also represent a reduction in production capacity at a certain moment and a problem in achieving the targeted final production objectives and the positioning of the company in the market. In many cases, and especially at the end

of the production cycle, the replacement of the lost stock represented by these mortalities is very difficult, so during a certain period, the farm runs at suboptimal production capacity. Even survivor fish stocks can represent a problem for the farm, as smaller stocks, in certain conditions, can be much more difficult to manage than a standard stock. Although substantial improvements, including a shortening of the production cycle, have been achieved in aquaculture and fish farming in the last few decades [90] production cycles in fish farming are still relatively long (3–4 years in salmon, 16–24 months in European seabass and gilthead seabream, 8–20 months in rainbow trout or 5–8 months in Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*, depending on their final size at harvesting and the temperatures), compared to other terrestrial livestock such as pigs (6–7 months) or particularly poultry (7 weeks). In longer cycles, mortalities tend to be particularly penalizing for the company. When mortalities in the farm are associated with infectious or parasitic diseases, the presence of fish carcasses in the facility can significantly reduce the hygiene conditions of the water and can be a high risk for the rest of the stock. Mortality should be quickly removed and disposed of adequately, and this usually represents an unexpected extra production cost. Only in a very few cases can a small amount of revenue be obtained when dead fish carcasses can be preserved and stored as silage [91] or similar methods. In the EU, these materials can be used as animal by-products (ABPs) if they correspond to category 3 (low risk material), but in most cases, they are considered as ABP category 2 (intermediate risk material) according to Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1774/2002 on animal by-products regulation and could eventually be processed as hydrolyzed by-products. For these reasons, if the risk of future mortalities is too high, controlled emergency harvesting in certain conditions can be advisable.

6.3 | Morbidity

The dual combination of morbidity/mortality is usually referred to when discussing the main effects of disease and is widely used in areas such as epidemiology [92]. However, in the context of assessing the disease burden in fish farming, these two terms have very different approaches. As described previously, the burden and impact of mortality resulting from a disease event can be assessed in a relatively simple way through a combination of the losses and value of the fish at each moment. However, morbidity is much more difficult to address in the context of burden assessment.

Morbidity is usually described from an epidemiological point of view as the incidence rate of a disease. However, in a wider sense, morbidity can also address all the impacts associated with the condition resulting from the disease, such as a disorder or deviation from the normal health condition of the fish. In contrast with mortality, morbidity can cause even more effects related to disease burden, as sick fish have lower zootechnical performance, require even better management and feeding compared with healthy stocks, and in many cases, should also be treated, sometimes without a guarantee of their survival or a complete recovery of their zootechnical capacities. The effects of disease outbreaks in fish farms may be multiple and focus on different aspects. A short summary of different types of impacts is indicated in Table 3.

Alterations in fish performance are typically observed during outbreaks, or with chronic diseases, and the impact is clearer when performance is affected over a long period or cannot be recovered or can only be partially recovered. Reduced food intake and growth, and increased feed conversion rates are typically observed in many parasitic diseases such as sea lice [93], and particularly in diseases affecting the digestive system. These include viral diseases that have the exocrine pancreas as one of their target organs, such as pancreas disease in Atlantic salmon [94], or IPN in salmonids [95], bacterial diseases specifically affecting the digestive tract, such as rainbow trout gastroenteritis [96] or enteric parasites affecting the intestinal mucosa such as *Enteromyxum* or *Enterospora* in gilthead seabream; these can lead to a reduction in the feed intake for many days or lower performance, due to problems in the digestion, absorption, or metabolic use of the nutrients in the feeds [97]. Gill diseases, particularly in Atlantic salmon farming, also represent an important multifactorial cause of economic losses, impacting various aspects such as welfare, performance, the decisions of fish farm managers, and potentially leading to increased secondary infections. These diseases can alter the respiratory capacity and ion regulation of fish, which can result in decreased aerobic activity [98] influencing both the growth and feed conversion ratio.

Problems related to the commercial value of the fish mainly affect the last stages of the production cycle, close to harvesting or when fish should be sold, for example as juveniles from nurseries. Diseases producing external skin and/or fin lesions such as ulcers (winter ulcer, sea lice in salmon, ectoparasitic crustacea in other species), external hemorrhages (strawberry/red mark disease in salmonids, petechial rash in seabream and other species), skin alterations (lymphocystis), fin and skin necrosis and damage in *Flavobacterium* sp. and *Tenacibaculum* sp. infections in salmonids and many other fish species [99], or abscess-like lesions in muscle in *Senegalese sole* (*Solea senegalensis*) by the amoeba *Endolimax piscium* [100], may cause higher economic impact in these stages. Other problems can be found in the post-harvesting commercial value of the fish, mainly from those diseases affecting the quality of the fish flesh, such as muscle melanosis due to HMSI in salmon [101], or parasites affecting the muscle such as *Kudoa* sp. [102]. Usually, these problems are not detected until the affected fish are processed, or are detected during routine health surveillance samplings. In many cases, the impact of these problems is concentrated in the number of fish per harvested batch rejected in the processing plant, or in a downgrade of the quality of the fish, reducing the market value or limiting the use of the fish carcasses for food processing. For juveniles, the main burden associated with any infectious disease is the automatic rejection of these fish, or in some cases, the legal prohibition from being sold or transferred to another facility, causing serious problems for both supplier (immobilized stock) and customer (inability to start new production batches).

6.4 | Impacts of Diseases and Disorders in the Management Procedures at Farm Level

In many cases, disease outbreaks strongly alter routine farm management procedures and, in some cases, require specific

TABLE 3 | Main burden factors associated with disease-related morbidity.

Burden associated with morbidity	Description
Alterations in the fish performance	Alterations in feed intake (SFR), growth (SGR), feed conversion ratio (FCR) and indirectly, impact on production, harvesting and sales
Increased susceptibility to other diseases or pathological conditions	Weaker fish
Alterations related to the commercial value of the fish	External aspect or in the quality of the fish as food, decreasing the final value of the fish in the market or during processing
Costs associated with the management of diseases	Health and welfare management plans, surveillance, diagnostics, treatments, staff training and prevention and biosecurity investments. Costs increased when the disease is present
Indirect costs associated with immobilization of the fish stocks or alterations in the normal management programs	Grading, vaccination
Indirect costs associated with research into a particular new disease or problem	Costs of investment in research about the disease and in new vaccines or treatments. These costs are not necessarily passed on to the farm
Immobilization of the stocks or culling for sanitary reasons when the diseases are covered in national or international legislations	Losses mitigated by subsidies or private insurances
Indirect impacts related to the reputation (customers, external stakeholders, public opinion)	Impacts at farm/company level or involving the whole sector
Indirect impacts on the staff morale	The staff of fish farms are also emotionally sensitive to situations of health and welfare negatively affecting fish stocks

procedures that may cause stress for the fish, like crowding or manipulation. These specific husbandry operations can also provoke the expansion and expression of the disease in subclinical fish, higher mortality, or infection in other units. A delay in the implementation of these operations may be troublesome, requiring a reprogramming of the farming operations. All these indirect interferences with and changes in the forecasted production operations associated with disease events can cause a material reduction in farm productivity and decrease profitability. In addition, disease in farms can also be a notable source of tension for the staff of farms. Caring for fish and being faced with losses, sick fish, or a depopulation situation can create stress for fish farm staff, not only because of the impact on the fish farm economy but also due to the wasted time and dedication they have devoted to keeping the fish stocks and emotional links with the fish, as occurs with other farmed animal species.

6.5 | Economic Evaluation of the Costs Associated With the Management of Diseases: Surveillance, Diagnostics, Treatment, Prevention and Biosecurity Investments

Some studies addressing the economic costs associated with disease management in fish farms have been published [22, 76, 103], however, there are no clear guidelines or protocols on how to proceed for a comprehensive and balanced assessment of the economic and other impact of fish diseases. Public data on the real economic impacts of diseases in fish farming are scarce and fragmentary. In some cases, some information can be obtained based on conversations with farmers about their personal opinions and experiences and, less frequently, from more accurate and systematic data mining of the production databases of farms [104]. This is mainly due to the understandable desire of farms and companies to keep confidential their own production data as part of their proprietary “know how,” mainly to protect themselves against competitors, but also to avoid the misuse of these data and potential future reputational problems. This reluctance to release “private open data” is even stronger if the data are related to health or welfare in terrestrial and aquatic farming, as these data can be even more sensitive than production data [105, 106]. This is not the case when diseases are reported under official surveillance programs or when regional, national or international authorities such as the WOA or disease reference laboratories require the reporting of monthly statistics on stocks, environmental conditions, diseases, or treatments. In these cases, it is compulsory for farms and companies to periodically provide data about certain diseases. In other cases, open data could be available from public research projects, mainly those involving farm-based health surveys or projects where fish farms, companies, or associations participate as partners and have internal surveys programmed. These types of economic evaluations require a range of international data that are no more often collected and recorded in larger scale fish farms and companies.

The global assessment of disease impact should cover all relevant aspects, such as evaluating losses due to mortality, morbidity and performance decrease, along with the overall investment in disease surveillance and control, including diagnostics, prevention and treatment. In a simple cost–benefit analysis, disease control

costs should ideally be lower than the difference between worst-case losses (without implementing any control strategies) and current losses under implemented strategies. However, predicting costs without disease control is also difficult, making estimating efficiency ratios for surveillance and control strategies challenging. In addition, the costs of the different aspects of disease control (surveillance, diagnostics, prevention and control) may vary depending on the disease and the management approach taken, as well as the costs of the devices, materials, veterinary services or labor required. In general, these are the items that should be considered.

6.6 | Cost of Surveillance and Diagnostics

Disease surveillance in fish farms has a similar relevance to other animal farming activities in keeping diseases away from the farm, or at least, under control. For this reason, the implementation of internal disease surveillance programs in fish farms is always recommended. For certain diseases under official surveillance, the corresponding authorities are responsible for overseeing sampling and supervision. However, in many cases, and especially when the country is free of noticeable diseases, the non-notifiable diseases represent the main source of disease problems affecting fish farms. For these non-notifiable diseases, the responsibility for costs of surveillance depend on the policies of farms and companies, or the services provided by professional aquatic health providers. These costs are usually important, since surveillance usually requires a considerable effort in sampling and in the analysis and interpretation of results by specialists in fish health. Table 4 summarizes different categories of expenses usually associated with disease surveillance costs in fish farms.

It is very important to develop efficient sampling plans and select the most suitable samples according to their diagnostic value and the epidemiological characteristics, in order to increase the sampling efficiency and minimize time and costs. The cost of diagnostics is much more difficult to assess, as they cannot be previously scheduled and may vary strongly according to the complexity of each case and the characteristics of the farm. The cost of the diagnostics could be estimated based on the results of previous years and the costs of surveillance.

6.7 | Cost of Control

Treatments should be considered as a reactive strategy focused on reducing the impacts of a disease at farm level. When the disease can be controlled through a combination of therapeutic and management measures, the decision about the use of a certain control strategy, or even not using one, is usually taken after a cost–benefit analysis. In fish farming, as indicated in the previous sections, is not always easy to predict the evolution of a disease outbreak and assess the burden. It is even more difficult to assess whether the investment in time, dedication and economic resources in its control and treatment will be effective enough to compensate for the losses associated with the disease problem, unless the farm has had previous experiences with the same disease. In any case, a preliminary assessment of the costs related to treatment is always necessary. In some farmed terrestrial animals (dairy cows, for example), clinical approaches for

TABLE 4 | Different categories of costs associated with health sampling surveys at farm level and specific issues related to each category.

Categories	Specificities
Supervision and sampling labour	Samplings should be defined, programmed and supervised by a fish health expert. Samplings should be performed by trained personnel
Consumable materials (anaesthesia, sampling, storage, media, preservation solutions)	Related to the required sampling: Non-lethal: blood sampling, fin clipping, biopsies, skin scrapings, gill/skin swabs... Lethal sampling: Necropsy and tissue sampling for histopathology, virology, microbiology, parasitology or molecular biology
Sample submission	When samples should be submitted to external laboratories. Costly, as requires specific biosafety containers
Analysis	Costs according to the different types of analysis and diagnostic techniques required
Interpretation labour	Interpretation should be performed by fish health experts

individuals or small groups of animals are still possible but become much more difficult for bigger groups (e.g., swine or poultry farming). In fish farming, the focus is on very large groups of animals (thousands, hundreds of thousands and sometimes, millions of fish). In these cases, treatments are delivered collectively following the concept of metaphylaxis [107] as a “diseased stock,” independently of the number of animals affected, thus requiring higher amounts of therapeutic products and labor.

In addition to the economic cost, the use of therapeutic products in finfish farming, as in terrestrial farming, may also have a material impact on public opinion, mainly related to safety and environmental issues [68]. In some situations, such as farms with organic or ecological fish farming certifications, medications are prohibited or strictly controlled. Although in Europe, strong regulations on food security and environmental protection are issued under the umbrella of relevant institutions such as the EMA and EFSA, the sensitivity of stakeholders and public opinion on this topic should not be disregarded.

To sum up, the final objective of the treatments in fish farms is to reduce the burden or impacts associated with a disease at the farm level, but the treatments also have their own burden and impacts. In each disease event and scenario, the economic balance between costs and benefits and the general balance between the pros and cons should be assessed because, in some cases, the burden of treatment could be higher than the reduction in the impact of the

disease itself. In fish farming, there are two main ways to deliver treatments: oral and bath, each one with different costs.

6.7.1 | Oral Treatments: Constraints and Costs

Oral treatments in fish farming are mainly based on the addition of therapeutics (antibiotics or antiparasitics) together within the feeds, whereas bath treatments mainly consist of adding therapeutic chemical substances (salt, formalin, hydrogen peroxide and other substances), and occasionally antiparasitics, into the water.

The production and use of oral treatments may be technically very complex and require specialized knowledge [60, 62] and may imply important financial costs, mainly when a high biomass of fish needs to be treated. In some European countries, medicated feeds can be produced locally (after a veterinary prescription is issued and after approval by the competent authorities) by mixing and binding the therapeutic products with the feed on the same farm. However, this is a system that can only be applied to treat batches with a reduced number of fish as it requires significant labor, and according to the national legislation, in some European countries it is not possible. For bigger batches, medicated feeds are usually provided by the feed suppliers, requiring some extra time for administrative permissions, medicated feed production logistics, and transportation to the farm. The time required for this process is also critical, as in many cases, fish cannot be treated until several days after the disease has been diagnosed, by which time fish appetite may be highly reduced, thus decreasing the efficiency of the treatment. At the farm level, medicated feeds require more labor, as they should be delivered by hand or by carefully monitoring the feed intake when delivered through automatic feeders. It should be noted that the costs of these medicated feeds are usually much higher than standard feeds. Another relevant issue and constraint related to treatments is the reduced knowledge about pharmacological actions and the metabolite residue permanence of the therapeutic molecules in fish, compared to terrestrial farmed animals [60, 108, 109]. In addition, it is important to stress that the availability of commercial medicines for fish disease treatments in farms in each country can be a relevant issue. In Europe, due to the strict regulations on the use of the therapeutic molecules and medicines that can be legally applied in animal farming, and the reduced number of licensed products specifically for farmed fish, there is a severe scarcity of commercial products available for treatments in Europe [110]. Regarding the costs of oral medication, the cost of the commercial medicines and also the cost of manufacturing the medicated feed should be considered, as well as the calculation of the waste of medicines during the process, the amount of uneaten medicated feeds, the non-absorbed products, and finally, although usually intangible, the potential impacts on the environment.

6.7.2 | Bath Treatments: Constraints and Costs

Bath treatments are another treatment option widely used in fish farming, mainly to treat external diseases and parasitic infections in the gills or skin. This type of treatment is mainly suitable for fry or juvenile fish, as many fish can be treated in each treatment, although it is also feasible but more complex for bigger fish,

especially if biomasses are not too high. The feasibility, logistics, and cost of bath treatments also depend on the rearing system used in the farm. Baths performed in tanks are usually easier to deliver and control. This can be done in systems operating in flow-through systems (using a static or dynamic bath) or in RAS systems. Baths in ponds and cages have a higher complexity, as fish should be netted and moved to a treatment container or into a barge, or tarpaulins and similar devices should be placed in cages for 'in situ' treatments, requiring larger volumes of therapeutics [60, 62]. For these reasons, the cost of the treatments may vary significantly according to the treatment required, the population to be treated, and the volume of water required. As standard costs associated with bath treatment in tanks, in addition to the cost of the product to be used, labor costs for the operation of implementation and supervision, as well as the cost of the required equipment (tanks, nets, pumps, hand nets), should be considered. Man-labor costs of bath treatments can be different, according to the complexity of the treatments, and particularly high for treatments in cages, when specialized personnel (divers, crane operators) and equipment (auxiliary boats) are required. Additionally, a feed withdrawal period prior to bath treatment is usually applied. The stress produced by fish handling during bath treatment operations can also be considered a negative issue to be taken into consideration, as well as the potential environmental impact of the substances released into the environment after the treatments.

Concerning the availability of products in Europe and in the EU, there is only a limited range of approved substances for bath treatments that can be used under the current EU legislation, as well as a reduced number of commercial products.

6.8 | Non-Medicinal Treatments: Constraints and Costs

Bath and oral treatments can be performed with medicinal substances, but alternative non-medicinal therapeutic treatments are also available for certain fish diseases, mainly against sea lice in salmon, using de-lousing systems that include biological control with cleaner fish, thermal, mechanical (brushing, flushing), freshwater bath and laser-based devices [111]. In these cases, logistics are also complicated, as fish should be manipulated and pumped on board to be processed through machinery. The costs of the machinery (purchase, maintenance, renting) are also high. If the use of some of this equipment is not done properly, potential losses (mortality, lesions, stress, secondary infections) can be present. Similar to bath treatments, a period of starvation before treatments is applied, slightly increasing the rearing time required until harvest. The use of cleaner fish for parasite biological control also leads to important issues in terms of financial costs and environmental and welfare impacts [112], and the cleaner fish (mainly wrasses and lumpfish) can also be affected by an important number of diseases [113].

6.9 | Cost of the Investments Related to Risk Assessment and Prevention at Farm Level

Due to the extremely important impacts associated with the presence of diseases in fish farms, as well as the limited options

for efficient treatments in fish farming due to the specific characteristics mentioned before, risk assessment, prophylaxis and disease prevention have become very important for farmed fish health and welfare management [114].

Prevention is strongly related to risk assessment, so the implementation or improvement of prophylactic measures and systems in fish farming [53], is carried out mainly to reduce the risk of entrance, expansion and, in many cases, also dispersion, of diseases to the environment or to other facilities. Fish disease risk assessment has been particularly addressed in the last two decades [115–117] although the focus has been mainly on specific disease surveillance programs and disease dispersion modeling under a general epidemiological vision, and less on risk assessment at specific farm level. There is a general but vague acceptance of the positive effects of the implementation of biosecurity and preventive measures at farm level, but there is, in many cases, an important uncertainty related to how efficient and cost-effective these measures are in the reduction of the risk of entrance of a particular disease, or different diseases in a facility. Small-scale, retrospective analyses can be conducted within a company to assess the gains or losses associated with the implementation of a biosecurity measure. Unfortunately, there are no predictive models described. In a few cases, expert opinions [117] allow a certain consensus, but not reliable qualitative analysis. Due to this scarcity of comparative data based on real cases of diseases in aquatic farmed animals, it is particularly difficult to infer specific risk rates that could be used to assess the efficiency of the implementation of these measures at farm or company level. This also has relevance for aquaculture insurance, as for example, it is much easier to calculate risks associated with rough weather conditions than diseases.

Concerning biosecurity, there is extensive scientific and technical literature on general strategies to implement biosecurity in aquaculture and fish farming [118, 119]. However, due to the vast diversity of farmed fish species, farming systems and technologies applied, the standardization of biosecurity for the whole aquaculture or fish farming industry is almost impossible, so each specific case and site will require tailor-made recommendations adapted to the specific characteristics of the farm site, commercial activities, sanitary risks, production technology used, water quality and other characteristics.

In terrestrial animal farming, there are still limited studies about the direct benefits that prevention and biosecurity investments can produce for farms, even in traditional farmed species, such as pigs or poultry [120], and in fish farming the number of studies is even lower [121]. In fish farming, as the measures to be applied can be different in each situation and scenario, the costs of the implementation of preventive measures at fish farm level are difficult to evaluate. Some of the prevention and biosecurity measures and tools summarized in Table 5 can be easily implemented, but many others involve much greater complexity or require radical changes in the farm infrastructures, or even in the production procedures.

In addition, calculating the cost-benefits balance related to implementing new preventive measures or strategies to reduce the impact of a certain disease or diseases is extremely difficult, even more difficult than in treatments, unless this

evaluation is conducted on particular fish farms, based on the previous experience of the farm with different prevention and biosecurity strategies, and by using specific, risk analysis tools. Without these evaluations, decisions about which are the most appropriate strategies to adopt are always particularly challenging. The decision, in many cases, should be taken on the basis of an overall solution, which is optimal, and not solely based on the apparent and immediate financial impact on the farm's or company's financial bottom line. Often, in fish farming production, in opposition to other evident costs such as feeds and feeding or labor costs, costs related to health and disease management or prevention are considered expendable extra costs, as they are associated with risks and not with an absolute necessity like feeds.

6.10 | Cost-Benefits of Immunoprophylaxis and Vaccination

Amongst the different preventive measures that can be implemented in fish farms, there is a consensus that the development of specific vaccines for fish, and the development of systematic vaccination plans at the farm level, represent the most significant milestones in fish disease prevention. Unlike biosecurity and other preventive measures, such as the use of nutraceutical products, functional feeds, and health-focused nutritional programming, vaccines offer a much clearer and even quantifiable value in terms of risk assessment, and several papers on the economy of vaccination have already been published [122, 123]. This is because any commercial vaccine provides data from the manufacturer, validated by official national and international agencies, about its efficacy, that can be easily extrapolated to protection levels. For certain vaccines, efficacy values from laboratory experiments are provided, but for some vaccines, valuable data about the field efficacy through pilot farm tests and company follow-up could also be available. In these cases, calculations of the cost-benefits concerning the protection against specific diseases can be easily carried out, particularly if the farm or company already has data about the losses and costs associated with previous outbreaks without vaccination. For these evaluations, several items such as the cost of the vaccine dose per fish, the logistical costs of the vaccination process, the post-vaccination mortality, and recovery time (days to achieve normal behavior, feeding and growth) should be evaluated. Concerning the vaccination process, recent technological developments in vaccination automation may have a relevant impact on the cost of the vaccination process, compared with manual operations that usually require higher manual labor [124].

6.11 | Welfare

In addition to prevention and prophylaxis, good welfare practices have been claimed to play a certain role in the reduction of the risk of diseases [125]. This statement is mainly associated with the improvement in the general physiological health condition, absence of stressors and therefore, resilience of the fish against diseases. However, as in prophylaxis and biosecurity, it is particularly difficult to assess quantitatively the impact of the implementation of positive welfare measures in

TABLE 5 | main aspects related to the costs of the implementation of different prevention/biosecurity strategies in fish farming.

Prevention/biosecurity measures	Comments
Barriers in the facility: footbaths, personal hygiene and disinfection equipment	Easy to implement but require regular maintenance. Low cost. Efficacy related to the risks associated with the movements of personnel.
Zoning/isolation	Usually requires major changes and renovation works.
System cleaning and disinfection: Tanks, pipes, filters, biofilters, aerators, oxygen system	High complexity in some cases and extensive labour required. Difficult to perform in a farm still in operation. Highly efficient when a pathogen is established in the system.
Farm equipment cleaning and disinfection: nets, tank cleaning devices, handnets, pumps, graders, classifiers, removable pipes, hatchery equipment, automatic feeders, probes	Easier to implement but requires constant supervision, discipline and implementation in SOPs. Extensive labour required.
Downtime/following	High cost for the farm for long following periods (no production during downtime). Acceptable costs if it is well programmed in between production batches.
Water treatment: UV, ozone, and so forth	Implementation according to farm characteristics and disease risk assessment (water source, hatchery/nursery). Costs variable, according to the system and water volume to be treated.
Hygiene protocols	Specialist required in the development of the protocols. Protocol execution and supervision required. Labour costs.

the reduction of the risk of certain diseases in a fish stock. There are some examples of epidemiological or laboratory studies [126–128] that indicate some positive effects of the implementation of specific welfare measures or husbandry improvement in the reduction of the expression and impact of fish diseases, but these results cannot be extrapolated to all cases and scenarios. In other studies [129], it was highlighted the potential increase of bio-economical productivity factors in the rainbow trout industry and of consumers' willingness to pay, associated with the implementation of specific welfare interventions. In the last decade, through the EU BENEFISH project, some areas of potential added value by improving fish welfare in a variety of species and farming systems within European aquaculture were also identified [130]. Further studies are necessary to demonstrate and visualize the benefits of using certain strategies to improve welfare in fish farming and fish husbandry and reduce the impact of diseases. Moreover, welfare assessment programs at farm level are becoming a relevant issue for the industry and for the authorities in Europe, and particularly in the EU. Welfare is already one of the most important aspects covered by aquaculture certification schemes, and official welfare supervision in fish farms by the competent authorities will be implemented in the next few years.

6.12 | Health and Diseases Coverage in Aquaculture Insurances

Aquaculture insurance is highly recommended, specially under certain conditions, due to the fact that the industry has a particularly high number of operational risks because of its exposure to different types of so-called 'named perils'. Amongst these perils, aquaculture and specifically fish farming is highly exposed to pollution events, damages associated with extreme weather conditions (both inland and marine facilities), predation, harmful plankton blooms, mechanical or electrical breakdown or accidental damage to machinery (pumping systems), problems with oxygen supply or accidents related to other maritime activities (collision with boats). In the past, losses associated with diseases were included in most insurances, but in many cases in a vague way, and it was not clearly indicated when the losses associated with a disease could be claimed as "accidental losses associated with an inevitable event." This uncertainty caused many legal disputes between the insurance companies and the farm holding the insurance. This weakness was detected by many companies and nowadays, the conditions for the coverage of disease episodes are much clearer. For the insurance companies, the criteria for an "unavoidable" and "unpredictable" event is very important in providing the insurance, so companies tend to refuse to cover diseases that can be prevented through a reasonable biosecurity and prophylaxis system, if there is an available commercial vaccine, or if they can be treated with reasonable success. Companies also tend to refuse to cover diseases that are officially under national or international surveillance programs, as they usually have their own compensatory systems. For this reason, losses associated with incorrect or antiquated fish disease management practices would no longer covered by the insurers, highlighting further the need to improve good health practices in farms.

6.13 | Impact on Fish Health of Health Certifications and Certification Schemes

Health certifications are documents that indicate certain particularities related to the health status of a certain fish stock (absence of disease or pathogens, vaccination, etc.). Certificates should be issued and signed by aquatic/fish health expert professionals to be legitimate and as a guarantee of the sanitary status of the fish stock. In the case of official requirements related to administrative procedures, certificates are issued by official authorities. These health certificates usually have relevant legal effects in activities under administrative surveillance (transportation, active surveillance programs) and also in commercial operations, especially when live fish or other aquatic animals are involved in these transactions. Health certifications, therefore, are also relevant elements in fish farming and aquatic animal health management as they are proof or guarantee of higher health standards, consequently reducing disease risk levels and providing evidence for insurers to increase the trustworthiness of the good health practices of the insured company. In addition, these certificates can facilitate other operations such as the movement of the aquatic animal stocks.

Certification schemes in aquaculture have become a powerful system for accrediting quality and good production practices, and on marketing terms are also considered as a valuable instrument to increase the societal and consumer perception of the sector and improve the acceptance and credibility of companies [131]. As health and welfare is a very important component in industry practices, farm procedures related to both components, health management and welfare, are carefully examined and considered in all the certifications. Higher standards in disease prevention and management are requested and, if not achieved, this can be one of the reasons for loss of the certification. The negative effects of non-certification on the prestige of a company, and of the impossibility to operate with other certified companies, cannot be undervalued.

6.14 | Fish Health and Fish Diseases Modelling in Farms

An assessment of the effects of implementing different fish health management strategies in the performance of fish farms or fish farm companies requires powerful and realistic models to allow accurate and wise decisions. Disease modelling, and particularly economic modelling are particularly strategic in human health and human disease management and are considered essential tools for human epidemiologists, public health managers, pharmaceutical companies, and health technology-related industries. Models allow the generation of predictive future scenarios of the evolution of diseases and allow the exploration of different potential complex scenarios focusing on health economic aspects. These models have been developed from complex mathematical models to obtain algorithms, subsequently using more advanced systems such as Bayesian inference, and nowadays using new tools of big data, machine-learning, and AI. These sophisticated models allow the generation of precise and robust predictive results that can be used for decision-making. These models can also be used in the fish farming sector [132] and can be easily upgraded particularly

when the system for a model can be fed with reliable and harmonized big data obtained from production and health performance indicators collected from as many production batches as possible. Although some papers [22, 23, 76] have introduced the relevance of the economic assessment of farmed fish diseases through modelling, the future development of accurate models based on specific fish diseases will not only allow the prediction of patterns and behaviors, but also the accurate prediction of economic consequences.

7 | Concluding Remarks

To sum up, the evaluation of the disease burden in the context of fish farming requires a complex and integrative analysis, involving many different aspects, including technical, economic, geographic, political, and societal aspects as well as aspects related to environmental and long-term sustainability. An accurate and global visualization of all the aspects represented under the context of the diseases burden in the fish farming industry in Europe will allow a proper evaluation of the real impacts associated to the diseases in their facilities, increasing the awareness concerning these impacts and invest in the implementation of strategies and measures to reduce these impacts.

Author Contributions

Francesc Padros: conceptualization (lead); writing-original draft (lead); formal analysis (lead); writing - review and editing (equal). **Hamish Rodger:** conceptualization (equal); formal analysis (equal); writing - review and editing (equal). **Maria Constenla:** formal analysis (equal); writing - review and editing (equal). **Ana Herrero:** formal analysis (equal); writing, review and editing (equal). **Maurice Glucksmann:** formal analysis (equal); writing - review and editing (equal). **Alberto Allepuz:** formal analysis (equal); writing - review and editing (equal). **Carlos Zarza:** formal analysis (equal); writing - review and editing (equal).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

References

1. S. Nomura and A. Ishizuka, "Chapter 2.3 Disease Burden: Generating Evidence, Guiding Policy," in *WHO Guidance on Research Methods*

for Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management (World Health Organization, 2020), 64–76, <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665>.

2. W. Gilbert, T. L. Marsh, G. Chaters, et al., "Quantifying Cost of Disease in Livestock: A New Metric for the Global Burden of Animal Diseases," *Lancet Planetary Health* 8, no. 5 (2024): 309–317, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(24\)00047-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00047-0).

3. P. H. Schwartz, "Risk and Disease," *Perspectives in Biology and Medicine* 51, no. 3 (2008): 320–334, <https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.0.0027>.

4. D. E. Bloom, S. Chen, M. Kuhn, M. E. McGovern, L. Oxley, and K. Prettnner, "The Economic Burden of Chronic Diseases: Estimates and Projections for China, Japan, and South Korea," *Journal of the Economics of Ageing* 17 (2020): 100163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeoa.2018.09.002>.

5. F. Hessel, "Burden of Disease," in *Encyclopedia of Public Health*, ed. W. Kirch (Springer, 2008), 94–96, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5614-7_297.

6. S. H. Sokolow, N. Nova, I. J. Jones, et al., "Ecological and Socioeconomic Factors Associated With the Human Burden of Environmentally Mediated Pathogens: A Global Analysis," *Lancet Planetary Health* 6, no. 11 (2022): 870–879, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00248-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00248-0).

7. D. G. J. Larsson and C. F. Flach, "Antibiotic Resistance in the Environment," *Nature Reviews. Microbiology* 20, no. 5 (May 2022): 257–269, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-021-00649-x>.

8. J. D. Moreno-Ternero, T. T. Platz, and L. P. Østerdal, "QALYs, DALYs, and HALYs: A Unifying Framework for the Evaluation of Population Health," *Journal of Health Economics* 87 (2023): 102714, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2022.102714>.

9. B. J. McMahon, S. Morand, and J. S. Gray, "Ecosystem Change and Zoonoses in the Anthropocene," *Zoonoses and Public Health* 65, no. 7 (2018): 755–765, <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12489>.

10. J. P. Graham, J. H. Leibler, L. B. Price, et al., "The Animal-Human Interface and Infectious Disease in Industrial Food Animal Production: Rethinking Biosecurity and Biocontainment," *Public Health Reports* 123, no. 3 (2008): 282–299, <https://doi.org/10.1177/003335490812300309>.

11. A. Kappes, T. Tozoneyi, G. Shakil, et al., "Livestock Health and Disease Economics: A Scoping Review of Selected Literature," *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 10 (September 2023): 1168649, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1168649>.

12. FAO, "Economic Analysis of Animal Diseases," FAO Animal Production and Health Guidelines. No. 18. Rome, 2016, <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/ba43dfb4-ed6c-4690-b588-38973030279d/content>.

13. K. Raymond, N. BenSassi, G. T. Patterson, et al., "Informatics Progress of the Global Burden of Animal Diseases Programme Towards Data for One Health," *Revue Scientifique et Technique* 42 (2023): 218–229, <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.42.3365>.

14. B. Huntington, T. M. Bernardo, M. Bondad-Reantaso, et al., "Global Burden of Animal Diseases: A Novel Approach to Understanding and Managing Disease in Livestock and Aquaculture," *Revue Scientifique et Technique* 40, no. 2 (2021): 567–584, <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.40.2.3246>.

15. K. Amenu, K. M. McIntyre, N. Moje, et al., "Approaches for Disease Prioritization and Decision-Making in Animal Health, 2000–2021: A Structured Scoping Review," *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 10 (October 2023): 1231711, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1231711>.

16. A. A. Dijkhuizen, R. B. M. Huirne, and A. W. Jalvingh, "Economic Analysis of Animal Diseases and Their Control," *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 25, no. 2 (1995): 135–149, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5877\(95\)00535-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5877(95)00535-8).

17. J. Rushton, *The Economics of Animal Health and Production* (CABI, 2009).

18. A. P. Shinn, J. Pratoomyot, J. E. Bron, et al., "Economic Costs of Protistan and Metazoan Parasites to Global Mariculture," *Parasitology* 142, no. 1 (2015): 196–270, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031182014001437>.
19. H. D. Rodger, "Fish Disease Causing Economic Impact in Global Aquaculture," in *Fish Vaccines*. Birkhäuser *Advances in Infectious Diseases*, ed. A. Adams (Springer, 2016), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-0348-0980-1_1.
20. R. P. Subasinghe, J. Delamare-Deboutteville, C. V. Mohan, and M. J. Phillips, "Vulnerabilities in Aquatic Animal Production," *Revue Scientifique et Technique* 38, no. 2 (September 2019): 423–436, <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.38.2.2996>.
21. F. Asche, J. L. Anderson, R. Botta, et al., "The Economics of Shrimp Disease," *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology* 186 (2021): 107397, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2020.107397>.
22. E. J. Peeler, R. Caballero-Celli, C. E. S. Davila, et al., "Farm Level Bio-Economic Modelling of Aquatic Animal Disease and Health Interventions," *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 221 (December 2023): 106055, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2023.106055>.
23. A. Aunsmo, D. Persson, M. Stormoen, S. Romstad, O. Jamtøy, and P. J. Midtlyng, "Real-Time Monitoring of Cause-Specific Mortality- and Losses in Industrial Salmon Farming," *Aquaculture* 563 (2023): 738969, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738969>.
24. WOAAH, "Standard Operating Procedure for Determining Whether an Aquatic Animal Disease Should be Considered an Emerging Disease," 2023, <https://www.woah.org/app/uploads/2023/11/a-draft-sop-ed-aac.pdf>.
25. D. Little, R. Newton, and M. Beveridge, "Aquaculture: A Rapidly Growing and Significant Source of Sustainable Food? Status, Transitions and Potential," *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society* 75 (2016): 274–286, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0029665116000665>.
26. J. N. Cai, H. Huang, and P. S. Leung, "Understanding and Measuring the Contribution of Aquaculture and Fisheries to Gross Domestic Product (GDP)," in *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper*, vol. 606 (FAO, 2019), 80.
27. L. Appel, "La salmonicultura como motor económico: representa el 2,1% del PIB nacional," Salmonexpert Spa. Puerto Montt, Chile, accessed 15 February 2024, <https://www.salmonexpert.cl/empleo-estudio-salmonchile/la-salmonicultura-como-motor-economico-representa-el-21-del-pib-nacional/1503275/>.
28. T. Nyrud, A. Iversen, B. I. Bendiksen, R. Robertsen, and S. Steinsbø, "Sjømatnæringens ringvirkninger—Verdiskaping og ringvirkninger fra norsk sjømatnæring for 2022," Nofima rapportserie 27/2023.
29. B. Hersoug, E. Mikkelsen, and T. C. Osmundsen, "What's the Clue; Better Planning, New Technology or Just More Money?—The Area Challenge in Norwegian Salmon Farming," *Ocean and Coastal Management* 199 (2021): 105415, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105415>.
30. Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs, Land Reform and Islands. Directorate Marine Directorate, "Scottish Fish Farm Production Survey 2022," 2023, Topic Marine and Fisheries.
31. M. Costello, "The Global Economic Cost of Sea Lice to the Salmonid Farming Industry," *Journal of Fish Diseases* 32, no. 1 (2009): 115.
32. E. Jakob, H. Stryhn, J. Yu, et al., "Epidemiology of Piscirickettsiosis on Selected Atlantic Salmon (*Salmo salar*) and Rainbow Trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) Salt Water Aquaculture Farms in Chile," *Aquaculture* 433 (2014): 288–294, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.06.018>.
33. F. Asche, H. Hansen, R. Tveteras, and S. Tveterås, "The Salmon Disease Crisis in Chile," *Marine Resource Economics* 24, no. 4 (2009): 405–411, <https://doi.org/10.1086/mre.24.4.42629664>.
34. B. Bustos, "Brote del virus ISA: crisis ambiental y capacidad de la institucionalidad ambiental para manejar el conflicto," *EURE (Santiago)* 38, no. 115 (2012): 219–245, <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0250-71612012003000010>.
35. D. Moran and A. Fofana, "An Economic Evaluation of the Control of Three Notifiable Fish Diseases in the United Kingdom," *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 80, no. 2–3 (2007): 193–208, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2007.02.009>.
36. A. Fofana and C. Baulcomb, "Counting the Costs of Farmed Salmonids Diseases," *Journal of Applied Aquaculture* 24, no. 2 (2012): 118–136, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454438.2012.663701>.
37. Y. Liu and H. V. Bjelland, "Estimating Costs of Sea Lice Control Strategy in Norway," *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 117, no. 3–4 (2014): 469–477, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.08.018>.
38. I. Lozano-Muñoz, J. Wacyk, C. Kretschmer, Y. Vásquez-Martínez, and M. C. Martín, "Antimicrobial Resistance in Chilean Marine-Farmed Salmon: Improving Food Safety Through One Health," *One Health* 12 (2021): 100219, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100219>.
39. Z. Sajid, A. K. Gamperl, C. C. Parrish, et al., "An Aquaculture Risk Model to Understand the Causes and Consequences of Atlantic Salmon Mass Mortality Events: A Review," *Reviews in Aquaculture* 16, no. 4 (2024): 1674–1695, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12917>.
40. I. Sommerset, J. Wiik-Nielsen, T. Moldal, et al., "Norwegian Fish Health Report 2022," in *Norwegian Veterinary Institute Report* (Norwegian Veterinary Institute, 2024).
41. Scottish Government, "Health Status of Fish and Shellfish Diseases in Scotland," 2022, <https://www.gov.scot/publications/health-status-of-fish-and-shellfish-diseases-in-scotland/>.
42. European Commission, "Farm to Fork Strategy for a Fair, Healthy and Environmentally-Friendly Food System," 2024, https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en#further-information.
43. WOAAH, "Aquatic Animal Code," 2024, <https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-do/standards/codes-and-manuals/aquatic-code-online-access/>.
44. J. Colville and D. L. Berryhill, *Handbook of Zoonoses: Identification and Prevention* (Mosby Elsevier, 2007).
45. E. Antuofermo, M. Polinas, D. Dessì, and F. L. Henriquez, "Editorial: Zoonosis Associated With Parasites and Infectious Diseases in Aquatic Animals," *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 10 (2023): 1227007, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1227007>.
46. F. J. Adroher-Auroux and R. Benítez-Rodríguez, "Anisakiasis and Anisakis: An Underdiagnosed Emerging Disease and Its Main Etiological Agents," *Research in Veterinary Science* 132 (2020): 535–545, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2020.08.003>.
47. G. Cammilleri, A. Costa, S. Graci, et al., "Presence of Anisakis Pegreffii in Farmed Sea Bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax* L.) Commercialized in Southern Italy: A First Report," *Veterinary Parasitology* 259 (2018): 13–16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2018.06.021>.
48. M. L. Fioravanti, A. Gustinelli, G. Rigos, et al., "Negligible risk of zoonotic anisakid nematodes in farmed fish from European mariculture, 2016 to 2018," *Eurosurveillance* 26, no. 2 (2021): 1900717, <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2021.26.2.1900717>.
49. D. T. Gauthier, "Bacterial Zoonoses of Fishes: A Review and Appraisal of Evidence for Linkages Between Fish and Human Infections," *Veterinary Journal* 203, no. 1 (2015): 27–35, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tvjl.2014.10.028>.
50. J. Y. Kim, M. H. Yi, and T. S. Yong, "Parasitic Infections and Medical Expenses According to Health Insurance Review Assessment Claims Data in South Korea, 2011–2018," *PLoS One* 14, no. 11 (2019): e0225508, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225508>.
51. D. L. Mitchum and L. E. Sherman, "Transmission of Bacterial Kidney Disease From Wild to Stocked Hatchery Trout," *Canadian*

- Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 38, no. 5 (1981): 547–551, <https://doi.org/10.1139/f81-077>.
52. L. H. Johansen, I. Jensen, H. Mikkelsen, P. A. Bjørn, P. A. Jansen, and Ø. Bergh, “Disease Interaction and Pathogens Exchange Between Wild and Farmed Fish Populations With Special Reference to Norway,” *Aquaculture* 315, no. 3–4 (2011): 167–186, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.02.014>.
53. B. Oidtmann, E. Peeler, T. Lyngstad, E. Brun, B. Bang Jensen, and K. D. Stärk, “Risk-Based Methods for Fish and Terrestrial Animal Disease Surveillance,” *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 112, no. 1–2 (October 2013): 13–26, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2013.07.008>.
54. J. Atalah and P. Sanchez-Jerez, “Global Assessment of Ecological Risks Associated With Farmed Fish Escapes,” *Global Ecology and Conservation* 21 (2020): e00842, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00842>.
55. P. Arechavala-Lopez, P. Sanchez-Jerez, J. T. Bayle-Sempere, I. Uglem, and I. Mladineo, “Reared Fish, Farmed Escapees and Wild Fish Stocks—A Triangle of Pathogen Transmission of Concern to Mediterranean Aquaculture Management,” *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* 3 (2013): 153–161, <https://doi.org/10.3354/aei00060>.
56. J. Abolofia, F. Asche, and J. E. Wilen, “The Cost of Lice: Quantifying the Impacts of Parasitic Sea Lice on Farmed Salmon,” *Marine Resource Economics* 32, no. 3 (2017): 329–349, <https://doi.org/10.1086/691981>.
57. Y. Liu, U. R. Sumaila, and J. P. Volpe, “Potential Ecological and Economic Impacts of Sea Lice From Farmed Salmon on Wild Salmon Fisheries,” *Ecological Economics* 70, no. 10 (2011): 1746–1755, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.04.017>.
58. T. A. Bakke, J. Cable, and P. D. Harris, “The Biology of Gyrodactylid Monogeneans: The ‘Russian-Doll Killers,’” *Advances in Parasitology* 64 (2007): 161–460, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-308X\(06\)64003-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-308X(06)64003-7).
59. T. Lieke, T. Meinelt, S. H. Hoseinifar, B. Pan, D. L. Straus, and C. E. W. Steinberg, “Sustainable Aquaculture Requires Environmental-Friendly Treatment Strategies for Fish Diseases,” *Reviews in Aquaculture* 12 (2020): 943–965, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12365>.
60. G. Rigos, D. Kogiannou, F. Padrós, et al., “Best Therapeutic Practices for the Use of Antibacterial Agents in Finfish Aquaculture: A Particular View on European Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) in Mediterranean Aquaculture,” *Reviews in Aquaculture* 13, no. 3 (2021): 1285–1323, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12523>.
61. A. Adenaya, M. Berger, T. Brinkhoff, M. Ribas-Ribas, and O. Wurl, “Usage of Antibiotics in Aquaculture and the Impact on Coastal Waters,” *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 188 (2023): 114645, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.114645>.
62. G. Rigos, F. Padrós, E. Golomazou, et al., “Antiparasitic Approaches and Strategies in European Aquaculture, With Emphasis on Mediterranean Marine Finfish Farming: Present Scenarios and Future Visions,” *Reviews in Aquaculture* 16, no. 2 (2024): 622–643, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12857>.
63. D. Schar, E. Y. Klein, R. Laxminarayan, M. Gilbert, and T. P. van Boeckel, “Global Trends in Antimicrobial Use in Aquaculture,” *Scientific Reports* 10 (2020): 21878, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78849-3>.
64. M. Cavallo, P. Raux, F. Massa, D. Fezzardi, and J. A. Pérez Agúndez, “Why Not? Decrypting Social Attitudes Toward European Aquaculture: An Updated Policy Perspective for an Old Problem,” *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management* 19 (2023): 896–909, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4663>.
65. D. Whitmarsh and M. G. Palmieri, “Consumer Behaviour and Environmental Preferences: A Case Study of Scottish Salmon Aquaculture,” *Aquaculture Research* 42 (2011): 142–147, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2010.02672.x>.
66. K. Bacher, A. Gordo, and E. Mikkelsen, “Stakeholders’ Perceptions of Marine Fish Farming in Catalonia (Spain): A Q-Methodology Approach,” *Aquaculture* 424 (2014): 78–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2013.12.028>.
67. A. Claret, L. Guerrero, R. Ginés, et al., “Consumer Beliefs Regarding Farmed Versus Wild Fish,” *Appetite* 79 (2014): 25–31, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2014.03.031>.
68. L. Reig, C. Escobar, M. Carrassón, et al., “Aquaculture Perceptions in the Barcelona Metropolitan Area From Fish and Seafood Wholesalers, Fishmongers, and Consumers,” *Aquaculture* 510 (2019): 256–266, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.05.066>.
69. K. Bacher, “Perceptions and Misconceptions of Aquaculture: A Global Overview,” 2015, GLOBEFISH Research Programme, Vol. 120, Rome, FAO. 35 pp.
70. J. Cantillo, J. C. Martín, and C. Román, “Understanding Consumers’ Perceptions of Aquaculture and Its Products in Gran Canaria Island: Does the Influence of Positive or Negative Wording Matter?,” *Aquaculture* 562 (2023): 738754, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738754>.
71. L. van den Boogaart, H. Slabbekoorn, and L. Scherer, “Prioritization of Fish Welfare Issues in European Salmonid Aquaculture Using the Delphi Method,” *Aquaculture* 572 (2023): 739557, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739557>.
72. M. G. Bondad-Reantaso, R. P. Subasinghe, J. R. Arthur, et al., “Disease and Health Management in Asian Aquaculture,” *Veterinary Parasitology* 132, no. 3–4 (2005): 249–272, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2005.07.005>.
73. Scottish Government, “Impacts of Lice From Fish Farms on Wild Scottish Sea Trout and Salmon: Summary of Science,” 2021, <https://www.gov.scot/publications/summary-of-information-relating-to-impacts-of-salmon-lice-from-fish-farms-on-wild-scottish-sea-trout-and-salmon/>.
74. L. Qviller, A. B. Kristoffersen, T. M. Lyngstad, and A. Lillehaug, “Infectious Salmon Anemia and Farm-Level Culling Strategies,” *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 6 (2020): 481, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00481>.
75. E. Lichtenberg and D. Zilberman, “The Econometrics of Damage Control: Why Specification Matters,” *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 68, no. 2 (1986): 261–273, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1241427>.
76. J. L. Fernández-Sánchez, A. Le Breton, E. Brun, et al., “Assessing the Economic Impact of Diseases in Mediterranean Grow-Out Farms Culturing European Sea Bass,” *Aquaculture* 547 (2022): 737530, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737530>.
77. J. A. Calderón Díaz, M. Rodrigues da Costa, L. Shalloo, et al., “A Bio-Economic Simulation Study on the Association Between Key Performance Indicators and Pluck Lesions in Irish Farrow-to-Finish Pig Farms,” *Porcine Health Management* 6, no. 1 (2020): 40, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40813-020-00176-w>.
78. A. Jones, T. Takahashi, H. Fleming, B. Griffith, P. Harris, and M. Lee, “Quantifying the Value of On-Farm Measurements to Inform the Selection of Key Performance Indicators for Livestock Production Systems,” *Scientific Reports* 11 (2021): 16874, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-96336-1>.
79. G. Trevisan, C. Johnson, N. Benjamin, L. Bradner, and D. C. L. Linhares, “Description of Changes of Key Performance Indicators and PRRSV Shedding Over Time in a Naïve Breeding Herd Following a PRRS MLV Exposure,” *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* 68, no. 6 (2021): 3230–3235, <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14327>.
80. R. Armengol, L. Fraile, and A. Bach, “Key Performance Indicators Used by Dairy Consultants During the Evaluation of Reproductive Performance During Routine Visits,” *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 10 (2023): 1165184, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1165184>.

81. T. Garlock, F. Asche, and J. Anderson, "Aquaculture Performance Indicators," Aquaculture America Conference 2021. San Antonio, Texas. Abstracts book. pp. 115.
82. T. M. Garlock, F. Asche, J. L. Anderson, et al., "Environmental, Economic, and Social Sustainability in Aquaculture: The Aquaculture Performance Indicators," *Nature Communications* 15 (2024): 5274, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49556-8>.
83. G. Marino, F. Cardia, T. Petoichi, and V. Donadelli, "Deliverable 7.1—Set of KPIs for Mediterranean Marine Fish Farming (MMFF) Sector," 2018, Project PerformFish Deliverable. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4551512>.
84. C. Kourkouta, A. Tsipourlianos, D. M. Power, K. A. Moutou, and G. Koumoundouros, "Variability of Key-Performance-Indicators in Commercial Gilthead Seabream Hatcheries," *Scientific Reports* 12 (2022): 17896, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-23008-z>.
85. R. Taylor, C. Huynh, D. Cameron, et al., "Gill Score Guide—Amoebic Gill Disease (AGD) Management Training Document," CSIRO Agriculture and Food, Tassal operations PTY Ltd and Marine Harvest ASA. 2016, <https://research.csiro.au/aquaculture/wp-content/uploads/sites/217/2018/03/Download-pdf-version.pdf>
86. J. Jeong and C. W. Revie, "Appropriate Sampling Strategies to Estimate Sea Lice Prevalence on Salmon Farms With Low Infestation Levels," *Aquaculture* 518 (2020): 734858, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734858>.
87. M. Villar-Torres, F. E. Montero, J. A. Raga, and A. Repullés-Albelda, "Diagnostic Strategies for Sparicotyle Chrysophrii Detection Based on Size-Variability and Site-Location," *Aquaculture Reports* 31 (2023): 101658, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2023.101658>.
88. T. Ellis, I. Berrill, J. Lines, J. F. Turnbull, and T. G. Knowles, "Mortality and Fish Welfare," *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry* 38 (2012): 189–199, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-011-9547-3>.
89. T. Kotani, M. Yokota, H. Fushimi, and S. Watanabe, "How to Determine the Appropriate Mortality in Experimental Larval Rearing?," *Fisheries Science* 77 (2011): 255–261, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12562-011-0329-8>.
90. R. L. Naylor, R. W. Hardy, A. H. Buschmann, et al., "A 20-Year Retrospective Review of Global Aquaculture," *Nature* 591 (2021): 551–563, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03308-6>.
91. K. V. Lo, P. H. Liao, C. Bullock, and Y. Jones, "Silage Production From Salmon Farm Mortalities," *Aquacultural Engineering* 12, no. 1 (1993): 37–45, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0144-8609\(93\)90025-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0144-8609(93)90025-7).
92. J. B. R. Hernandez and P. Y. Kim, "Epidemiology: Morbidity and Mortality," in *StatPearls [Internet]* (StatPearls Publishing, 2022).
93. D. Zhang, G. Sogn-Grundtvåg, and R. Tveterås, "The Impact of Parasitic Sea Lice on Harvest Quantities and Sizes of Farmed Salmon," *Aquaculture* 576 (2023): 739884, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739884>.
94. M. V. Røsæg, Å. H. Garseth, O. B. Brynildsrud, and M. D. Jansen, "Pancreas Disease Caused by Salmonid Alphavirus Subtype 2 Reduces Growth and Feed Conversion in Farmed Atlantic Salmon," *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 169 (2019): 104699, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2019.104699>.
95. M. Lillehammer, J. Ødegård, P. Madsen, B. Gjerde, T. Refstie, and M. Rye, "Survival, Growth and Sexual Maturation in Atlantic Salmon Exposed to Infectious Pancreatic Necrosis: A Multi-Variate Mixture Model Approach," *Genetics, Selection, Evolution* 45 (2013): 8, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9686-45-8>.
96. J. Del-Pozo, M. Crumlish, J. F. Turnbull, and H. W. Ferguson, "Histopathology and Ultrastructure of Segmented Filamentous Bacteria-Associated Rainbow Trout Gastroenteritis," *Veterinary Pathology* 47, no. 2 (2010): 220–230, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0300985809359381>.
97. A. Sitjà-Bobadilla and O. Palenzuela, "Enteromyxum Species," in *Parasites: Pathobiology and Protection*, ed. P. T. K. Woo and K. Buchmann (CAB International, 2012), 163–176.
98. M. Hvas, E. Karlsbakk, S. Mæhle, D. W. Wright, and F. Oppedal, "The Gill Parasite Paramoeba Perurans Compromises Aerobic Scope, Swimming Capacity and Ion Balance in Atlantic Salmon," *Conservation Physiology* 5, no. 1 (2017): cox066, <https://doi.org/10.1093/conphys/cox066>.
99. R. Avendaño-Herrera, A. B. Olsen, M. Saldarriaga-Cordoba, et al., "Isolation, Identification, Virulence Potential and Genomic Features of Tenacibaculum Piscium Isolates Recovered From Chilean Salmonids," *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* 69, no. 5 (2022): e3305, <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14606>.
100. M. Constenla, F. Padrós, and O. Palenzuela, "Endolimax piscium Sp. Nov. (Amoebozoa), Causative Agent of Systemic Granulomatous Disease of Cultured Sole, Solea senegalensis Kaup," *Journal of Fish Diseases* 37, no. 3 (2014): 229–240, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.12097>.
101. R. T. Kongtorp, T. Taksdal, and A. Lyngøy, "Pathology of Heart and Skeletal Muscle Inflammation (HSMI) in Farmed Atlantic Salmon Salmo salar," *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* 59, no. 3 (June 2004): 217–224, <https://doi.org/10.3354/dao059217>.
102. S. R. M. Jones and A. Long, "Increased Prevalence and Severity of Kudoa thyrstites (Cnidaria: Myxosporea) in Atlantic Salmon Salmo salar Exposed to Deeper Seawater," *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* 152 (2022): 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.3354/dao03702>.
103. A. Muniesa, D. Furones, C. Rodgers, and B. Basurco, "An Assessment of Disease Occurrence and Mortality in Marine Fish Farming in Spain," *Aquaculture Reports* 25 (2022): 101257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2022.101257>.
104. C. Atik, "Addressing Data Access Problems in the Emerging Digital Agriculture Sector: Potential of the Refusal to Deal Case Law to Complement Ex-Ante Regulation," *European Competition Journal* 19, no. 3 (2023): 380–409, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441056.2023.2200618>.
105. M. C. Gates, L. Earl, and G. Enticott, "Factors Influencing the Performance of Voluntary Farmer Disease Reporting in Passive Surveillance Systems: A Scoping Review," *Preventive Veterinary* 196 (2021): 105487, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105487>.
106. G. Enticott, L. Earl, and M. C. Gates, "A Systematic Review of Social Research Data Collection Methods Used to Investigate Voluntary Animal Disease Reporting Behaviour," *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* 69 (2022): 2573–2587, <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14407>.
107. A. Bousquet-Mélou, A. Ferran, and P. L. Toutan, "Prophylaxis and Metaphylaxis in Veterinary Antimicrobial Therapy," in *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Antimicrobial Agents Veterinary Medical*, Tel Aviv, Israel. 2010. pp. 11–15.
108. C. Michel and D. J. Alderman, "Chemotherapy in Aquaculture: From Theory to Reality," A Symposium, Paris, 12–15 March 1991. Paris: Office International des Epizooties.
109. B. T. Lunestad and O. Samuelsen, "Veterinary Drug Use in Aquaculture," in *Improving Farmed Fish Quality and Safety*, ed. Ø. Lie (Woodhead Publishing, 2008), 97–127, <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845694920.1.97>.
110. Federation of Veterinarians of Europe, FVE, "FishMedPlus—More Medicines for Fish," 2019, Brochures and Leaflets, <https://fve.org/publications/fishmedplus/>.
111. C. R. S. Thompson, A. Madaro, J. Nilsson, et al., "Comparison of Non-Medicinal Delousing Strategies for Parasite (Lepeophtheirus salmonis) Removal Efficacy and Welfare Impact on Atlantic Salmon (Salmo salar) Hosts," *Aquaculture International* 32 (2024): 383–411, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-023-01167-8>.
112. C. Garcia de Leaniz, C. Gutierrez Rabadan, S. I. Barrento, et al., "Addressing the Welfare Needs of Farmed Lumpfish: Knowledge Gaps,

- Challenges and Solutions,” *Reviews in Aquaculture* 14 (2021): 139–155, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12589>.
113. T. Erkinharju, R. A. Dalmo, M. Hansen, and T. Seternes, “Cleaner Fish in Aquaculture: Review on Diseases and Vaccination,” *Reviews in Aquaculture* 13 (2021): 189–237, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12470>.
114. P. Katharios, “Disease Prevention in Farmed Fish,” 2019, New Developments and Research Needs. Standing Committee on Agricultural Research, 48 pp., https://scar-europe.org/images/FISH/Documents/CASA_Fish_Disease_Final-Report.pdf.
115. E. J. Peeler, R. Gardiner, and M. A. Thrush, “Qualitative Risk Assessment of Routes of Transmission of the Exotic Fish Parasite *Gyrodactylus salaris* Between River Catchments in England and Wales,” *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 64, no. 2–4 (2004): 175–189, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2004.05.005>.
116. J. R. Arthur, M. G. Bondad-Reantaso, M. L. Campbell, et al., Understanding and Applying Risk Analysis in Aquaculture: A Manual for Decision-Makers FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper; No. 519/1. Rome, FAO. 2009, <https://www.fao.org/4/i1136e/i1136e00.htm>.
117. B. C. Oidtmann, I. Mladineo, A. Cook, et al., “Main Parasitic Infections in Gilthead Seabream and European Seabass Aquaculture: Risk Factors From Stakeholders’ Perspective,” *Aquaculture International* 32 (2024): 4303, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-024-01419-1>.
118. A. D. Scarfe and D. Palić, “Aquaculture Biosecurity: Practical Approach to Prevent, Control, and Eradicate Diseases,” in *Aquaculture Health Management*, ed. F. S. B. Kibenge and M. D. Powell (Academic Press, 2020), 75–116, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813359-0.00003-8>.
119. R. Subasinghe, V. Alday-Sanz, M. G. Bondad-Reantaso, H. Jie, A. P. Shinn, and P. Sorgeloos, “Biosecurity: Reducing the Burden of Disease,” *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 54, no. 2 (2023): 397–426, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12966>.
120. K. Roest, C. Montanari, P. Ferrari, et al., “Costs and Benefits of the Improvement of Biosecurity on Pig and Broiler Farms,” *Animal Research and Veterinary Science* 2023 (2023): 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.24966/ARVS-3751/100041>.
121. N. Zulfainarni and L. Megawati, “Cost of Biosecurity Application: Comparing Aquaculture System and Fish Health in Traditional Fish Farm,” in *Proceedings of the Conference of the International Society for Economics and Social Sciences of Animal Health—South East Asia (ISESSAH-SEA 2019)*, <https://doi.org/10.2991/isessah-19.2019.27>.
122. R. Thorarinnsson and D. B. Powell, “Effects of Disease Risk, Vaccine Efficacy, and Market Price on the Economics of Fish Vaccination,” *Aquaculture* 256, no. 1–4 (2006): 42–49, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.01.033>.
123. M. K. Bedekar and S. Kole, “Fundamentals of Fish Vaccination,” in *Vaccine Design: Methods and Protocols, Volume 2. Vaccines for Veterinary Diseases*, ed. S. Thomas (Springer, 2022), 147–173, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1888-2_9.
124. P. J. Midtlyng, “Current Use and Need for New Fish Vaccines,” in *Principles of Fish Immunology*, ed. K. Buchmann and C. J. Secombes (Springer, 2022), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-85420-1_19.
125. H. Segner, H. Sundh, K. Buchmann, et al., “Health of Farmed Fish: Its Relation to Fish Welfare and Its Utility as Welfare Indicator,” *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry* 38 (2012): 85–105, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-011-9517-9>.
126. T. R. Cecil, “Husbandry and Husbandry-Related Diseases of Ornamental Fish,” *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Exotic Animal Practice* 2, no. 1 (1999): 1–18, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1094-9194\(17\)30137-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1094-9194(17)30137-8).
127. J. M. Ramsay, V. Watral, C. B. Schreck, and M. L. Kent, “Husbandry Stress Exacerbates Mycobacterial Infections in Adult Zebrafish, *Danio rerio* (Hamilton),” *Journal of Fish Diseases* 32, no. 11 (2009): 931–941, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2761.2009.01074.x>.
128. P. Tedesco, M. Saraiva, J. V. Sandoval-Sierra, et al., “Impact of Abiotic Factors and Husbandry on Saprolegniosis in Salmonid Farms,” *Aquaculture* 561 (2022): 738679, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738679>.
129. M. Kankainen, I. K. Berrill, C. Noble, et al., “Modeling the Economic Impact of Welfare Interventions in Fish Farming—A Case Study From the U.K. Rainbow Trout Industry,” *Aquaculture Economics & Management* 16, no. 4 (2012): 315–340, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13657305.2012.729248>.
130. C. Noble, I. K. Berrill, B. Waller, et al., “A Multi-Disciplinary Framework for Bio-Economic Modelling in Aquaculture: A Welfare Case Study,” *Aquaculture Economics & Management* 16, no. 4 (2012): 297–314, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13657305.2012.729250>.
131. V. S. Amundsen and T. C. Osmundsen, “Becoming Certified, Becoming Sustainable? Improvements From Aquaculture Certification Schemes as Experienced by Those Certified,” *Marine Policy* 119 (2020): 104097, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104097>.
132. I. F. Tvete, M. Aldrin, and B. B. Jensen, “Towards Better Survival: Modeling Drivers for Daily Mortality in Norwegian Atlantic Salmon Farming,” *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 210 (2023): 105798, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2022.105798>.